

Supplemental Table 3. Data charting for all studies included in the scoping review.

Author	Year of publication	Country	Study design	Source of GWG data; guideline used	Characteristics of study sample	Sample size	Significant findings	Non-significant findings	Additional notes	Study sample primarily included individuals with a vulnerability									
										factor?	Education	Income	Marital status	Parity	Age	Race/ethnicity	Immigration status	Abuse	DOI
Alhusen, J. L.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth from 2004-11 and completed the Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System survey	251 342	Odds of excessive GWG increased by experiencing intimate partner violence (IPV) before pregnancy, young maternal age (<20 vs 30+ yrs) or if not married; odds of excessive GWG decreased if Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic or Asian non-Hispanic (as compared to White non-Hispanic), low education (<12 yrs vs 12+ years), low-income (0-200% of poverty line vs >200%), inadequate or intermediate prenatal care (as compared to adequate); odds of insufficient GWG increased if Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic or Asian non-Hispanic (as compared to White non-Hispanic), low education, low-income, not married, inadequate/intermediate /adequate plus prenatal care (as compared to adequate prenatal care); odd of insufficient GWG decreased if age 20-24 or 25-29 (vs 30+ yrs old)	NS effect of young maternal age (<20 yrs as compared to 30 yrs or older) or IPV before and/or during pregnancy; NS effect of American Indian/Alaska Native non-Hispanic on excessive or insufficient GWG; NS effect of IPV during or before and during pregnancy, or adequate plus prenatal care (vs adequate prenatal care) on excessive GWG	Abused women were significantly more likely to smoke during pregnancy, to report inadequate prenatal care, be single, younger, less educated, and have lower income; greater proportion of Black non-Hispanic women suffered abuse	No	S	S	S			S & NS	S & NS	S & NS	10.1016/j.jogn.2016.12.003
	2012		Cross-sectional	Medical records; IOM 2009	Black women ≥18 yrs of age receiving prenatal care at a university hospital for women on community-based insurance; all women had a BMI ≥25 kg/m ²	120		No correlation between GWG and parity											10.1155/2012/878607
Allison, K. C.		USA																	
Ancrì, G.	1977	USA	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Single-site study with women age 12-32 years; all women were White (with the exception of one Black woman)	98	Significantly higher GWG in adolescents (18-19 yrs) than in adults (20-24 years, 25-32 years); significantly lower GWG in oldest age group									S			American Journal of Clinical Nutrition 1977;30:568-572
Ba'aqeel, H. S.	1989		Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents and adults who gave birth at a university hospital between January 1983 and December 1984, the majority of whom were Saudi; all women were married	184		NS difference in GWG between adolescents (age ≤18 yrs) and adults (age 20-29 yrs); note: more than half of the adolescents were 18 yrs of age, and a similar proportion of adults were 20-22 yrs of age								NS			Annals of Saudi Medicine 1989;9(2):144-149
		Saudi Arabia																	
Bahadoer, S.	2015	Netherlands	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Multiethnic population-based cohort of women who were pregnant in Rotterdam from 2001-05	6 444	Surinamese-Hindustani and Moroccan women had lower risks of excessive GWG and lower GWG (vs. Dutch women)	NS difference between in total GWG for Cape Verdean, Dutch Antillean, Surinamese-Creole, and Turkish women vs Dutch women									S & NS		10.1016/j.ejogrb.2015.06.031
Beaudrot, M. E.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Population-based cohort of primiparous adolescents and adults who gave birth in Ohio from 2006-12	251 398	Adequacy of GWG (lost weight, insufficient GWG, adequate GWG, or excessive GWG) differed significantly between age groups (<15 yrs, 15-17 yrs, 18-19 yrs, and 20-34 yrs); no post hoc tests for GWG adequacy and age									S*			10.1038/jp.2016.61
Berenson, A. B.	1997	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents <18 years who received prenatal care at an adolescent obstetrics clinic (single-site)	337	Young adolescents (<15 years old) were more likely to have insufficient GWG; higher odds of insufficient GWG in adolescents who were physically abused (vs. no abuse), had a STD (vs. no STD) during pregnancy, or with an unplanned pregnancy (vs. planned); significant differences in proportion of women with GWG <20 lbs vs ≥20 lbs by race/ethnicity (Black, Mexican-American, White, other)	NS association between being currently enrolled in school, poverty level, marital status, parity, employment status, initiation of prenatal care or number of prenatal visits to GWG (compared adolescents gaining <20 lbs to those gaining 20+ lbs)	Insufficient GWG was defined as <20 lbs as prior studies have associated this amount with LBW infant; insufficient GWG in a little over 1/10 women	Yes		NS	NS	NS	S*	S	S	American Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology 1997;176(6):1220-7	
Beydoun, H. A.	2011	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Respondents of the 2000-06 Oklahoma Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System who were ≥20 years of age	11 561	Asian women, multiparous women, and those using alcohol during last 3 months of pregnancy had higher odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG); higher education was a protective factor against insufficient GWG; young (20-34, as compared to 35+ years old), unmarried, nulliparous women had higher odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG), as did women with higher education (>12 yrs vs <12 yrs); physical violence by an intimate partner around the time of pregnancy (before and/or during) was positively and significantly associated with insufficient and excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) only among women ≥35 years	Physical abuse before and/or during pregnancy not associated with excessive or insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) in younger women (age 20 - 34 years); NS association with odds of excessive GWG if 12 yrs education vs <12 yrs education; NS association with odds of insufficient vs adequate GWG in unmarried women (as compared to married women) or in women with parity 1 (vs parity 0); NS difference in odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) by race/ethnicity (White, Black, Native American, Asian); NS difference in odds of inadequate GWG (vs adequate GWG) by race/ethnicity for women who were White, Black, or Native American		S & NS		S & NS	S & NS	S* & NS*	S & NS	S & NS	S & NS	10.1016/j.socscimed.2011.01.006	

Bjermo, H.	2015	Sweden	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women included in the Swedish Medical Birth Register from 1992-2010	378 529	Higher risk of excessive GWG in normal weight women with low education (high school or less) vs. high education (university education or doctoral degree); in overweight/obese women: slightly lower risk of excessive GWG if low education (vs. high education) (adjusted RR)		No	S							10.1186/s12889-015-1624-6	
Bogaerts, A.	2012	Belgium	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women who delivered in Flanders in 2009	54 022	Women with high/highest education levels (Bachelor degree or masters/doctorate degree) had lower odds for excessive and insufficient GWG (vs. medium education, i.e. full high school education); higher odds of insufficient GWG in very low education (primary school only); single status (vs. living with partner) and low maternal age (≤ 24 years vs. 25-29 years) had higher odds of excessive GWG; higher maternal age (35-44 years) had lower odds of excessive GWG; higher odds of insufficient GWG in 20-34 year old & women >45 years; multiparous had lower odds of excessive GWG and higher odds of insufficient GWG; higher odds of excessive GWG if Dutch or Turkish and lower odds in Moroccan (as compared to Belgian), lower odds of insufficient GWG if Turkish but higher odds if Moroccan (as compared to Belgian); being without employment (as compared to actively employed) decreased odds of excessive GWG and increased odds of insufficient GWG	NS effect of Dutch ethnicity (compared to Belgian) on insufficient GWG; NS effect of very low (primary school) or low (some high school) education on excessive GWG (as compared to medium education, i.e. full high school); no effect of low education (as compared to medium) on odds of insufficient GWG; NS effect of age 30-34 on odds of excessive GWG; NS effects of age <20 or 35-44 years on insufficient GWG	No	S & NS	S	S	S & NS	S & NS				10.1111/cob.12004
Bombard, J.	2012	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Multi-state study involving women who responded to the Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2005-06	14 990	Significantly higher prevalence of insufficient GWG in low-income women (as compared to high-income women); with adjusted OR, near-low-income women (as compared to high income women) had significantly higher odds of having insufficient GWG than adequate GWG	NS difference in prevalence of excessive GWG between low-income and higher income; with adjusted OR, NS difference in odds of excessive GWG vs adequate GWG for low-income or near-low-income women (as compared to high income women), and NS difference in odds of insufficient vs adequate GWG in low-income women as compared to high-income women	No		S & NS						10.1007/s10995-010-0717-1	
Cameron, R. P.	1996	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Pregnant White and Black women (18-40 years old) from three obstetric clinics for low-income women	132	Weight deviation (calculated on the basis of recommended weight for height and adjusted for medically ideal weight gain during pregnancy) increased significantly for Black women from prepregnancy to the 2nd trimester, but remained constant for White	Black women were less likely to be married and to live with a partner and reported higher self-esteem	Yes					S			Health Psychology 1996;15(4):293-7	
Caulfield, L. E.	1996	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Black and White women who delivered at John Hopkins Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics from 1987-89	3 870	Increased odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) if Black; lower odds of insufficient GWG if higher education (>12 years vs 12 years); lower odds of excessive GWG if parous (≥ 1); significant difference in mean age between GWG adequacy categories (but not specific to adolescents vs adults)	NS effect of parity on insufficient GWG; NS effect of being Black or higher education (>12 years vs 12 years) on excessive GWG; NS effect of low education (<12 years as compared to 12 years) on insufficient or excessive GWG	No	S & NS		S & NS	S*	S & NS			Obstetrics and Gynecology 1996;87(5, Part 1):760-6	
Cavicchia, P. P.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in South Carolina from 2004-06	132 574	Significant differences in adequacy of GWG between racial/ethnic groups (no post-hoc tests)		No					S			10.1007/s10995-014-1437-8	
Chaffee, B. W.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Individuals in the 1979 cohort of the National Longitudinal Survey of Youth (age 14-21 in 1979) who gave birth before the age of 40	4 780		Risk ratio for excessive GWG based on growing up in a household that was <200% or <100% of federal poverty line was NS for all women (sub-divided by race/ethnicity: non-Black non-Hispanic; Black non-Hispanic, and non-Black Hispanic)	No		NS†						10.1186/s12982-015-0026-7	
Chagarlamudi, H.	2018	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women attending an outpatient obstetrics/ gynecology clinic that mainly serves a low-income community (2012-13) in North Carolina	410		NS effect on odds of having excessive or insufficient GWG (as compared to adequate GWG) by age, low-income status (indicated by Medicaid or lack of insurance), or race/ethnicity (White, Black, Hispanic/other); NS difference in education levels (\leq grade 11, high school graduate/GED, some college/vocational school, or college graduate or higher) between women who had insufficient, adequate, or excessive GWG	Yes	NS	NS†		NS	NS			10.14423/SMJ.000000000000756	
Chandra, P. C.	2002	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Primarily unmarried Black and Hispanic adolescents and adults who gave birth at a public urban hospital from January 1996 to October 1999	2 352	Young adolescents had significantly lower GWG than older adolescents and adults	Adolescents had lower prepregnancy BMI than older group; more Hispanic women in the younger group	No					S			International Journal of Gynecology and Obstetrics 2002;79:117-22	

Chang, T.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women aged 15-24 years living in large US cities from 1998-2000; national weights were used to make data representative of births in all large US cities (populations of >200,000); all women were part of the "Fragile Families and Child Wellbeing Study"	1,034 (unweighted)	Hispanic women had lower risk of excessive GWG than non-Hispanic women	NS association between age (range of 15-24 years), race (Black or other as compared to White) or poverty level on excessive or insufficient GWG; Hispanic ethnicity not associated to insufficient GWG	More than half of sample exceeded GWG recommendation; prepregnancy BMI was significantly associated to GWG	No	NS		NS*	S & NS		10.1371/journal.pone.0173790		
Chasan-Taber, L.	2016	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 293	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, or excessive) according to level of education (categories: < high school, high school graduate, some college/graduate) and immigration status (born in continental US vs Puerto Rico/Dominican Republic)	Age (age range: 16-40 years old), income, (<\$15,000, \$15,000-30,000, >\$30,000), marital status (single/divorced/separated/widowed vs married), living with partner/spouse, parity (0, 1 or 2+) and acculturation not associated with adequacy of GWG	Nearly half of women were overweight/obese prior to pregnancy; approximately one-fifth of women gained below IOM recommendation and over half above recommendation	Yes	S	NS	NS	NS	NS*	S	10.1007/s10995-016-1983-3	
Chasan-Taber, L.	2014	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic women (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) seeking prenatal care at a public clinic from 2006-11	1 276	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, or excessive) according to level of education (categories: < high school, high school or GED, some college/graduate) and immigration status (categories: woman born in Puerto Rico/Dominican Republic, parent born in PR/DR, or grandparent born in PR/DR); women with highest levels of occupational activity were less likely to have insufficient GWG (vs. unemployed women)	NS difference in adequacy of GWG according to age (age range: 16-40 years old), household income (<\$15,000, \$15,000-30,000, >\$30,000), marital status (single/divorced/separated/widowed vs married), if living with spouse/partner, level of acculturation or parity (0, 1, or 2+)	Majority of women were unmarried and almost half were overweight/obese; more than half of women had excessive GWG and nearly a quarter has insufficient GWG; women reporting major depression more likely to have insufficient GWG, measured using 10-item Edinburgh	Yes	S	NS	NS	NS	NS*	S	10.1002/oby.20549	
Chasan-Taber, L.	2008	USA	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	Hispanic (primarily Puerto Rican), low-income women receiving prenatal care at a public clinic from 2000-03	770	Lower risk of excessive GWG if <10 years of residence in USA (compared to third generation women), parous; higher risk of excessive GWG in women 30-39 years old (as compared to 20-24 years old)	NS effect of living 10+ years in USA or being a second generation immigrant (as compared to third generation) on excessive or insufficient GWG; NS effect of living <10 years in USA (as compared to being third generation immigrant) parity, or age on insufficient GWG; NS effect of younger age (<20 or 25-29 yrs vs 20-24 yrs) on odds of excessive GWG; education (< high school, high school/trade/technical school, college), household income (<\$15,000, 15,000-30,000, >30,000), and number of adverse life events were not significantly associated to GWG	Approximately half of women gained above IOM guidelines, whereas nearly a quarter gained below guideline	Yes	NS	NS	S & NS	S* & NS	S & NS	10.1038/oby.2008.256		
Cheng, H. R.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	White non-Hispanic and Asian-American non-Hispanic (Asian Indian, Chinese, Filipino, Japanese, Korean, or Vietnamese) women who were documented in the 2009 Texas birth certificate data	114 632	Asian women had higher odds of insufficient GWG and lower odds of excessive GWG (vs. White non-Hispanic); among Asian women: higher odds of insufficient GWG in Asian Indian, Filipino, Japanese, Korean, and Vietnamese (as compared to Chinese), older women (18-34 years vs 35+ yrs), and foreign born; lower odds of insufficient GWG if primiparous; higher odds of excessive GWG in Asians who are unmarried, have some college education (as compared to high school or less) and primiparous; lower odds of excessive GWG in Asians who are foreign-born	NS difference in odds of excessive GWG according to Asian subgroup, age, if higher educated (university degree vs high school or less); NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG if unmarried or according to level of education: NS difference in odds of excessive or insufficient GWG according to Medicaid status (yes vs no)		No	S & NS	NS†	S & NS	S	S* & NS*	S & NS	S	10.1016/j.whi.2015.01.003
Chihara, I.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Low income women who were enrolled in Hawaii's Special Supplemental Nutrition Program for Women, Infants, and Children from 2003-05	19 130	Significant difference in GWG adequacy based on maternal age (<20, 20-29, 30+ yrs), education (< 12 years, 12 years/high school, >12 years), race/ethnicity (Hawaiian/part Hawaiian, Asian, White, Pacific Islander, other), marital status (married vs unmarried), parity (no previous live birth vs one+ previous live births), and enrollment in Medicaid/TANF/Food Stamps (yes/no)		Nearly half of sample were overweight/obese prepregnancy; almost two-thirds of women had excessive GWG, whereas one-fifth had insufficient GWG	Yes	S	S†	S	S	S*	S	10.1007/s10995-013-1342-6	
Clayborne, Z. M.	2017	Canada	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Women age ≥16 years living in two metropolitan areas in Alberta	2 068	Higher odds of excessive GWG with lower neighbourhood SES	Neighbourhood SES not associated to insufficient GWG		No							10.1016/j.socscimed.2016.12.041	

Cohen, A. K.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth who were 14-22 years old in 1979	2 769	Women with normal prepregnancy weight with less education had higher odds of excessive GWG (as compared to adequate GWG; education categories: not graduated from high school and graduated from high school vs. college students); less education protected against excessive GWG among Black women (less than a high school degree vs high school degree); White women with less than a high school degree were more likely to have excessive GWG than those who graduated high school and those with a college degree; less education increased odds of insufficient GWG (less than high school vs college & high school vs college).	NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG if less than high school degree, as compared to high school degree; NS interaction by race/ethnicity on odds of insufficient GWG by educational attainment; NS effect of education on excessive GWG in Hispanic or overweight women; NS difference in odds of excessive GWG if high school degree vs college degree for all race/ethnicities; NS effect of less than high school vs high school on odds of excessive GWG between normal weight and overweight women	No	S & NS					S & NS	10.1016/j.whi.2016.05.009		
Cruickshank, A.	2018	Australia	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Women ≥18 years who delivered at a hospital in a socially disadvantaged area south of Brisbane	399	Significant differences in GWG adequacy, with Maori and Pasifika women more likely to report excessive GWG (vs. other groups), Maori and Pasifika women also had significantly higher GWG		No							S	10.1016/j.wombi.2017.11.003	
Cunningham, S.D.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women age 14-21 yrs old enrolled in the CenteringPregnancy Plus RCT (a multi-site prenatal care intervention) from 2008-2012; hospitals chosen for the RCT primarily served women who have low income and women from minority groups	505		Women having adequate vs excessive GWG did not differ by mean age, race/ethnicity (Latina, Black non-Latina, or other), or marital status (married/living with partner vs other)	Yes		NS		NS	NS			10.1111/jmwh.12686	
D'Angelo, D. V.	2012	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	PRAMS data from women who gave birth in 27 different states in 2008, all of which had a PRAMS survey response rate of 65% or greater	35 980		NS difference in adjusted odds of gaining >35 lbs vs ≤35 lbs in women with Medicaid as compared to private medical insurance	No		NS†							10.1007/s10995-012-1172-y
Deputy, N. P.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Participants of the 2010-11 Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System	44 421	<u>Underweight</u> : higher odds of insufficient and excessive GWG with education less than high school (compared to high school); lower odds of insufficient GWG if nulliparous and consumed alcohol during pregnancy; higher odds of insufficient GWG if nonmarried. <u>Normal weight</u> : higher odds of insufficient GWG if NH Black, Hispanic, Asian (as compared to White), lower education (<12 yrs vs 12 yrs); lower odds of excessive GWG if Asian; lower odds of insufficient GWG if nulliparous (vs parous), while higher odds of excessive GWG if nulliparous. <u>Overweight</u> : higher odds of insufficient GWG if Black, Indigenous (Alaskan Native) (compared to White), Medicaid enrollment (yes/no); higher odds of excessive GWG if education more than high school (vs high school), age under 19 (vs 25-29 yrs), nulliparous. <u>Obese</u> : lower odds of insufficient GWG if Asian, Indigenous (Alaskan Native), nulliparous; lower odds of excessive if Indigenous (Alaskan Native); higher odds of excessive GWG if nulliparous, unmarried	Age: NS effect of adolescent age on excessive or insufficient GWG for all BMI groups (except overweight - higher risk of excessive GWG); race/ethnicity: NS effect on GWG adequacy in any BMI group for Native American, Hawaiian, and other; education: NS effect of higher education (>12 yrs vs 12 years) on GWG adequacy (except in overweight - higher risk of excessive GWG); parity: NS effect of parity on excessive GWG in underweight group and on insufficient GWG in overweight group; marital status NS on GWG adequacy for all groups except underweight (higher odds of insufficient GWG if unmarried) and obese (higher odds of excessive GWG if unmarried); income: NS effect of WIC enrolment on GWG adequacy across all groups; NS effect of Medicaid enrollment in all groups but overweight (higher risk of insufficient GWG)	No	S & NS	S† & NS†	S & NS	S & NS	S & NS	S & NS	10.1097/AOG.000000000000739		
Djakovic, I.	2019	Croatia	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; no GWG guideline identified	Women in their second pregnancy at a single site university hospital	113	Higher total GWG in low education (high school educated vs college/university)		No		S						10.3889/oamjms.2019.141	
Elchert, J.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Population-based cohort of primiparous women who gave birth in Ohio from 2006-12	326 368	Increased risk of insufficient GWG in adolescents (vs adults age 20-34 yrs); lower risk of excessive GWG in 15-17 year olds vs adults	NS difference in excessive GWG risk between adolescents <15 and 18-19 yrs old and adults (age 20-34)	No						S & NS		10.1016/j.jpeds.2015.05.043	
Fernandez, I. D.	2011	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Population registry of adolescents who gave birth in Upstate New York from 1996-2002	6 995	Significant differences in total GWG by parity (0, 1, or 2+ live births), race (White, Black, other)	Mean GWG did not vary significantly by age (<16 vs 16-20 yrs)	Yes				S	NS	S		10.1016/j.jpap.2011.06.009	
Fontaine, P. L.	2012	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Black and White women age 18-40 years who gave birth from 2004-07 in the Minneapolis-St. Paul metropolitan area	2 760	Adjusted multivariate analysis: White women had significantly greater total GWG compared to Black women (seen in normal weight, overweight and obese categories); significant difference in GWG adequacy between White and Black women (for normal, overweight, and obese)	NS difference in total GWG and GWG adequacy by race in underweight women	No						S & NS		10.1111/j.1542-2011.2011.00139.x	

Gaillard, R.	2013	Netherlands	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women in Rotterdam from 2001-05	6 959	Lower odds of excessive GWG if Non-European (vs Dutch/European ethnicity), multiparous (vs nulliparous), consumed alcohol during pregnancy	NS effect of education (primary or secondary vs higher education), age (mean age 30 yrs), or monthly household income (<€1,600 or €1,600-2,200, vs >€2,220) on odds of excessive GWG	Nearly half of sample had excessive GWG	No	NS	NS	S	NS	S	10.1002/oby.20088
Galn, J.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who delivered in California from 2007-12	2 364 793	Living in neighbourhoods with the highest quartile of violence was associated with excessive GWG (vs lowest quartile of violence) across all race/ethnicities; Asian/Pacific Islander and Hispanic had higher risk of excessive GWG in all levels of neighbourhood violence (when compared to low neighbourhood violence); decreased risk of insufficient GWG if neighbourhood violence only seen with Asian non-Hispanic/Pacific Islanders, and increased risk of insufficient GWG if multi-race non-Hispanic for neighbourhoods with low-medium and high levels of violence	NS difference in GWG adequacy by levels of neighbourhood violence for all other race/ethnicities	Half of women had excessive GWG and one-fifth insufficient GWG	No					S & NS	10.1111/ppe.12331
Galvez-Myles, R.	2005	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents (13-19 years) and adults (25-34 years) who delivered at 2 hospitals in Texas from January 1999 to April 2001 and were enrolled in the state's Medicaid program	685	Adolescents (≤19 yrs) had significantly higher total GWG than adults (remained significant after controlling for county type [rural or urban])	NS difference when total GWG of adolescents ≤17 yrs was compared to adult controls		Yes					S & NS	The Journal of Rural Health 2005;21(3):259-62
Gentry, J.	2014	USA	Prospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Participants from a smoking intervention program (a multi-site program) in Northeast Tennessee; women who experienced physical or sexual interpartner violence were excluded to assess the independent effect of psychosocial violence	489		NS difference in total GWG based on experiencing psychological abuse vs not experiencing psychological abuse		No				NS		10.1891/0886-6708.VV-D-13-00020
Gillespie, S. L.	2016	USA	Prospective	Medical record and measured; no GWG guideline identified	White and Black women who attended a university medical center or were from the surrounding community	105		NS difference in GWG by 2nd trimester and in total GWG between Black and White women		No				NS		10.1089/jwh.2016.5761
Gisladdottir, A.	2014	Iceland	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth between 1993 and 2011; a registry with women who sought services for sexual assault was used to identify women having experienced abuse	2 556		NS difference in adequacy of GWG (insufficient, adequate, or excessive) between women who experienced sexual abuse and those who did not		No				NS		10.1111/aogs.12331
Groth, S.	2008	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	Black, primiparous adolescents (12-19 yrs of age at the beginning of pregnancy) with a low income and at least two of three sociodemographic risk conditions: unmarried, <12 yrs of education, or unemployed	330		NS difference in total GWG based on age (<16 yrs, 16-17 yrs, 18-19 yrs)		Yes				NS		10.1002/nur.20243
Groth, S. W.	2018	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	White and Black women aged 18-35 with a BMI between 18.5 and 34.9 kg/m2 who participated in a RCT from 2009-14	774	Multiparous women had lower GWG than primiparous women when all BMI groups analyzed together (true for both gene groups); among Black women: low-income women (<185% of poverty line) with obesity gained significantly more weight than higher income women (>185% of poverty line) with obesity in one of two gene groups (FTO gene), but this difference was not observed among other BMI groups or when all BMI groups were combined; among White women: higher income normal-weight women had significantly lower weight gain in both gene groups (FTO and GNB3), but this difference was not observed in other BMI groups or when all BMI groups were combined	In most BMI groups and gene groups, income was not significantly associated with GWG for Black and White women; when parity was divided by BMI, differences in GWG did not remain significant (for all groups)		No		S & NS		S & NS		10.1016/j.nut.2017.11.008
Guillot, N.	2015	USA (Puerto Rico)	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women in northern Puerto Rico from 2011-14	160		NS associations were observed between GWG adequacy and age (18-29 years vs 30-40 years), education (high school education or less vs more than high school) or income (<\$20,000 vs \$20,000 or more)		Yes	NS	NS		NS*		10.1007/s10995-015-1764-4
Gutierrez, Y. M.	1999	USA	Prospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	Multi-site study with Hispanic (Mexican American), primiparous adolescents (13-18 years) in San Francisco and San Jose	46	Significant differences in GWG according to length of time living in the USA (3-12 mo, 12-48 mo vs 48-216 mo; time living in USA used as a proxy measure for acculturation)	Key exposure variable was acculturation, measure by the length of residence in the US		Yes				S		Journal of Adolescent Health 1999;25:227-37

Haeri, S.	2010	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	All births to adolescents at a single site from 2000-04	456		NS difference in adequate vs excessive GWG by age (≤ 15 yrs vs 16-18 yrs) or by race/ethnicity (Black, Hispanic, White)	Yes						NS	NS	10.1055/s-0029-1224866		
Haile, Z. T.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the population-based Infant Feeding Practices Study II from 2005-07	2 053		Significant differences in GWG adequacy by age (18-24 yrs, 25-34 yrs, 35+ yrs), marital status (never married, married, other), race/ethnicity (White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic, other), education (high school or less, some college, college graduate), poverty-to-income ratio (<185%, 185-349%, 350%+)	No	S	S	S			S*	S	10.1089/bfm.2016.0134		
Headen, I.	2018	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth who were 14-21 years old in 1979	3 300		Significant differences in GWG adequacy according to race/ethnicity (White, Black or Hispanic), marital status (married or unmarried), employment (unemployed, part-time, full-time), home ownership status, level of education (<12 yrs, 12-15 yrs, 16+ yrs), equalized income (divided in quartiles), and parity (0, 1, 2, 3, 4+); higher average cumulative neighbourhood deprivation was associated with increased risk of insufficient GWG (did not vary by ethnicity) and excessive GWG (only for White women); persistent low deprivation was associated with decreased risk of insufficient and excessive GWG (vs. high deprivation); upward mobility was associated with decreased risk of insufficient GWG across all ethnicities	No	S	S	S	S		NS*	S	NS	10.1016/j.healthplace.2018.05.007	
Headen, I.	2015	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth from 1979-2010 (all were part of the National Longitudinal Survey of Youth)	3 835		Black and Hispanic women had higher risk of insufficient GWG than White women (when divided into BMI categories, this remained true for all normal weight women; for underweight women: only true for Black women; for overweight and obese: risk of insufficient GWG did not vary by race/ethnicity)	No								S & NS	10.1007/s10995-015-1682-5	
Hediger, M. L.	1994	USA	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Women from Camden who were <16 yrs old (primiparous or multiparous) or were 18-29 yrs old (primiparous); women who reported breastfeeding following the birth of their child were excluded, as this can impact weight loss	608		NS difference in GWG at 28 weeks gestation, from 28 weeks gestation to delivery, or in total GWG between adolescents age 13-15 yrs, 16-18 yrs, or adults age 19-29 yrs	No								NS	Human and Clinical Nutrition 1994;124(1):24-30	
Hediger, M. L.	1997	USA	Retrospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Primigravida adolescents (<16 years) and adults (18-29 years) who gave birth from 1985-95 and were enrolled in the Camden Study	605		Compared to adults, adolescents had significantly higher GWG rate	No									S	10.1016/S1047-2797(97)00046-X
Hediger, M. L.	1989	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; based on clinical standards	Low-income adolescents registered in the Camden County Adolescent Family Life program from 1982-87	1 790		Significant differences in total GWG by race/ethnicity (Puerto Rican, Black, White), with White women gaining significantly more weight	Yes									S	American Journal of Human Biology 1989;1:665-672
Hediger, M. L.	1990	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Low-income adolescents registered in the Camden County Adolescent Family Life program from 1982-87	1 419		White had significantly higher GWG (vs. Black and Puerto Rican); primigravidity contributed significantly to higher GWG in last half of pregnancy; young age (≤ 14 years vs 17-18 yrs) was associated with higher weight gain from 20 wks gestation onward; smoking was associated to greater weight gain	Yes									S	American Journal of Clinical Nutrition 1990;52:793-799
Held, M. L.	2018	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; no GWG guideline identified	Undocumented Latina immigrant women (≥ 18 years old) from Guatemala or Mexico who gave birth in Nebraska from 2007-11	4 188		Excessive GWG more prevalent in Mexican than Guatemalan immigrants	Yes									S	10.1177/1540415318808829
Hernandez-Rivas, E.	2013	Spain	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Single-site study involving women who were monitored prenatally and gave birth from 2004-11	456		NS difference in total GWG by race/ethnicity (White vs Latin American, South-Central Asian, Moroccan, or East Asian)	No									NS	10.1016/j.diabetes.2013.01.030
Herring, S. J.	2012	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Urban, low-income, primarily Black women seeking prenatal care at a university hospital from 2009-11; all were receiving Medicaid	94		Nulliparity (vs. multiparity) and clinician advice discordant with IOM guidelines (vs. concordant advice) were significant predictors of excessive GWG	Yes	NS					S	NS*	NS	10.1016/j.whi.2012.05.004	

Hickey, C.A.	1997a	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Low-income, multiparous Black and White women with one or more risk factors for fetal growth restriction, who enrolled in prenatal care at specific university-operated clinics from 1985-88	806	Among Black women, having a mistimed or unwanted pregnancy, caring for more than one preschooler at home, and not having a car for errands were associated with increased odds of insufficient GWG (≤ 10 kg); among White women, those who worked over 40hrs/week had an increased odds of insufficient GWG	NS association between insufficient GWG and age, marital status, parity, education, household income, per capita income, source of income, utility disconnections (noted as being an indirect measure of financial stress), and participation in income-related assistance programs	Yes	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS*	S	10.1111/j.1523-536X.1997.00102.pp.x
Hickey, C.A.	1993	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Multi-site study involving Black or White women with a low-income who were pregnant with their 2nd or 3rd child and who were at risk of having a small-for-gestational-age infant	1 168		NS difference in total GWG between Black and White women	Yes						NS	Obstetrics and Gynecology 1993;81(4), 529-35
Hickey, C.A.	1992b	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; GWG evaluated as a percent of standard W/H (Rosso, 1985)	Low-income, Black and Hispanic women enrolled in prenatal care at two university-operated clinics	150	Unemployed women and those who lived in Dallas for a longer period of time (stated to be a potential surrogate variable for social support) had a decreased risk of low GWG ($< 120\%$ of standard prepregnancy weight for height), while women who smoked, had higher education, and were Black were at increased risk of low GWG (in univariate analysis: education was only significant for Hispanic women); in univariate analysis, marital status was significantly associated with GWG in Hispanic women (but NS for Black women), but was dropped from later multivariate models as it was a poor predictor of GWG when other variables were entered in model	NS association between low GWG and age (age range: 17-35 years), parity, perceived social support, marital status, and time of prenatal care initiation	Yes	S		NS	NS	NS*	S	10.1016/S0271-5317(05)80749-3
Hickey, C.A.	1992a	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Low-income, primarily Black, adolescents (< 20 years) with 2 completed pregnancies from 1983-90	152	Decreased weight gain in second pregnancy was significant for older adolescents (not significant in younger adolescents)		Yes						S & NS	10.1016/1054-139X(92)90369-M
Hoff, C.	1985	USA	Retrospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Nulliparous, primarily Black, low-income adolescents (< 17 years) and adults (17-31 years) who gave birth at a specific hospital in South Alabama from 1974-79	1 844	Adults: higher GWG in White women than Black women	NS difference in GWG between adults and adolescents of same race; in adolescents: NS difference in GWG between Black and White	Yes					NS	S & NS	American Journal of Diseases of Children 1985;139(10):981-6
Hollard, A. L.	2006	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Multi-site study with Black, White, and Hispanic women who had a previous cesarean section delivery and gave birth a second time from 1997-2002 in Southern California	5 589	Significant differences in prevalence of high GWG (> 13.6 kg) by racial/ethnic group (White, Hispanic, Black)		No						S	10.1080/14767050600847809
Hollingsworth, D. R.	1976	USA	Prospective	Not specified; no GWG guideline used	Unmarried, low-income, primiparous adolescents (age 12-18) who were admitted to a young mothers medical-obstetric service from 1971-74	406	Among adolescents with preeclampsia, White women had significantly higher total GWG than Black women	Among normal pregnancies (without complications and infants born of normal weight), there was no significant difference in total GWG between Black and White adolescents	Yes						S & NS	American Journal of Obstetrics & Gynecology 1976;126(2):230:237
Holowko, N.	2014	Sweden	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Primiparous women who gave birth from 1982-2008 and were in the third generation of the Uppsala Birth Cohort Study	4 080	Lower education increased odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) in normal weight women (elementary or secondary education vs tertiary education)	NS effect of education on GWG adequacy (excessive or insufficient GWG) for overweight/obese women; effect on underweight women could not be analysed with OR due to low statistical power (but NS difference in proportion of underweight women with insufficient/adequate/excessive GWG)	No	S & NS						10.1038/ijo.2013.62
Holowko, N.	2015	Sweden	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women with 2 pregnancies included in the Swedish Medical Birth Register and the Education Register from 1982-2010	163 352	Differing effects of education on adequacy of GWG (insufficient or excessive vs adequate) based on BMI and parity; in general: lower education was associated with higher odds of excessive GWG in underweight (1st pregnancy only) and normal weight women (1st and 2nd pregnancy); intermediate education reduced odds of insufficient GWG for underweight and normal weight women in 1st pregnancy; higher odds of insufficient GWG in overweight women with low/intermediate education (for 2nd pregnancy; 1st pregnancy: only associated with low education)	NS effect of education on GWG adequacy (odds of excessive or insufficient GWG, as compared to adequate) for obese women during pregnancy 1 or 2	No	S & NS					S & NS	10.1136/jech-2015-205598
Houde, M.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in the USA in 2012	3 960 796	GWG varied significantly between adults and adolescents		No						S	10.1016/j.jpap.2015.03.003

Howie, L. D.	2003	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Women included in the 2000 US Natality File (excluding women from California, as GWG there is not collected)	2 796 805	Odds of excessive GWG (>40 lbs) higher in adolescent (vs adult) and primiparous; lower odds of excessive GWG if lower education (less than high school for women 18 yrs or older, or if education was 6 or fewer years less than woman's age when <18 yrs old), older age, or of a racial/ethnic minority group (Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic/Latina, other vs White non-Hispanic)		No	S	S	S	S	10.1016/j.jada.2003.09.040
Huynh, M.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Primiparous women who gave birth from 1999-2001 in New York City, were ≥20 years old, and either White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, or Hispanic	56 911	Excessive GWG more likely in NH Black or Hispanic women than in NH White women, and in women living in low SES neighborhood compared to medium or high SES neighborhood; high school or some college increased risk of excessive GWG (compared to those with less than a high school education); lower odds of excessive GWG if NH White with college or more education; Hispanic women with high school or more education had higher risk of excessive GWG than those with less than high school education; women with at least high school education who are living in low or medium SES neighborhood have an increased risk of excessive GWG (compared to less than high school education); significant difference in prevalence of excessive GWG in women who use Medicaid when analyzed according to level of education (no sub-group analysis)	NS difference in prevalence of excessive GWG between highest and lowest levels of education (college or more vs less than high school education) when not divided by race/ethnicity and neighborhood SES; prevalence of excessive GWG did not vary by education level in Black non-Hispanic women, while White non-Hispanic women did not have a significant difference between high school education or some college when compared to less than high school education; NS difference in prevalence of excessive GWG according to level of education for those living in a high SES neighbourhood	No	S & NS	S†	S & NS	10.1007/s10995-013-1246-5	
Huynh, M. H.	2015	USA	Cross-sectional	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, or White non-Hispanic nulliparous adolescents (age 12-19) who gave birth in New York City from 2008-10	15 715	Non-immigrants have highest prevalence ratio of excessive GWG, and prevalence is lower as time lived in the US decreases (as compared to women who immigrated <5 years ago; results seen in all groups: race, insurance status and age [with the exception of age 12-15])	NS difference in prevalence of excessive GWG in youngest age group (12-15 years) according to immigration status	Yes			S & NS	10.1007/s10900-014-9914-y	
Incollingo Rodriguez, A. C.	2019	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women enrolled in the multi-site Community Child Health Network study who indicated that they experience everyday discrimination due to their weight or height	214	Self-reported discrimination based on weight associated with higher GWG and excessive GWG; primiparity negatively associated with excessive GWG	NS difference in odds of excessive GWG or total GWG according to race/ethnicity, age (age range: 18-40 years); NS difference in prevalence of excess GWG or in total GWG between racial/ethnic groups (White, Black, Latina); NS association between primiparity and total GWG	No		S & NS	NS*	NS	10.1037/hea0000711
Inoue, S.	2013	Japan	Cross-sectional	Measured; IOM 2009	Women who delivered at a specific hospital in Shizuoka Prefecture from 1997-2010	15 020	Among underweight women: higher odds of insufficient GWG if higher SES (office worker, professional worker or home-maker married to self-employed/ professional spouse, compared to home-makers married to salaried spouse), lower odds of insufficient GWG if consumed alcohol during pregnancy; lower odds of excessive GWG if age 25+ (as compared to <25 years); Among normal weight women: age >35 years was associated with higher odds of insufficient GWG, occupation status of home-maker married to self-employed/ professional spouse or professional worker lowered risk of excessive GWG (as compared to home-maker married to salaried spouse), older age (25+) decreased odds of excessive GWG; Among overweight women: age >35 decreased risk of insufficient GWG and alcohol consumption decreased risk of excessive GWG	Underweight women: NS effect of age on risk of insufficient GWG, NS effect of alcohol or occupation status on excessive GWG; normal weight women: NS effect of occupation status, age 25-35 (vs <25), or alcohol use on insufficient GWG and NS effect of some occupation status or alcohol use on odds of excessive GWG; overweight women: NS effect of age 25-35, alcohol use, or occupation status on insufficient GWG or age 25+, occupation status on excessive GWG	No		S & NS*	10.1007/s10995-012-1213-6		
Ishitsuka, K.	2019	Japan	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Adolescent (<20 years old) and adult (20-34 years old) women involved in the Japan Environment and Children's Study, a multi-site, nationwide cohort with deliveries from 2011-14	74 706	Differences in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, excessive) between adolescents (<20 yrs) and adults		No			S	10.1016/j.jpap.2018.10.009	

Johnson, P. J.	2002	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Primarily low-income, urban women seeking prenatal care at a specific clinic from 1997-98	578	<u>In adults</u> ; higher odds for insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) if any report of abuse (vs. no abuse; type and timing of abuse not considered), history of physical abuse only, history of physical abuse with or without history of physical abuse; higher odds of excessive GWG if history of sexual abuse with or without history of physical abuse, any abuse <u>When all subjects grouped together</u> : higher odds of insufficient GWG if history of physical abuse only <u>Distribution of women in GWG adequacy categories (insufficient, adequate, excessive)</u> : significant difference by education (looked at inadequate education, i.e. not having completed the expected number of years of schooling; only significant for adolescents), parity (1st birth vs 1+ previous birth; only significant for adults)	<u>In adolescents</u> : NS association between insufficient and excessive GWG and any type or timing of abuse; <u>in adults</u> : NS effect on odds of insufficient or excessive GWG if a woman experienced physical or sexual abuse during pregnancy; NS effect on odds of excessive GWG if a woman had a history of physical abuse only <u>When all ages grouped together</u> : NS effect of current physical/sexual abuse, history of sexual abuse with or without physical abuse, or any abuse on odds of insufficient or excessive GWG; NS effect of history of physical abuse only on odds of excessive GWG <u>Distribution of women in GWG adequacy categories</u> : NS association with age (looked at distribution within adolescents and adults, but did not compare adolescents to adults), alcohol use, or illicit drug use; <u>for adults only</u> : NS association with inadequate education; <u>for adolescents only</u> : NS association with	Yes	S & NS	S & NS	S & NS*	S & NS	Public Health Reports 2002;117(2):148-156	
Johnston, C. S.	1992	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Middle-class to upper-class women who gave birth under the care of the private CIGNA Healthplan of Arizona	329		NS difference in total GWG between adolescents (14-17 yrs old) and adults (18-25 yrs old)	No			NS		Journal of the American Dietetic Association 1992;92(12)	
Johnston, C. S.	1991	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	A subset of women who gave birth from 1987 to 1989 under the care of the private CIGNA Healthplan of Arizona	423		NS difference in total GWG, wt gain after 3 months of pregnancy or wt gain after 6 months of pregnancy between adolescents (14-17 yrs old) and young adults (18-25 yrs old)	No			NS		10.1080/07315724.1991.10718142	
Joseph, N. P.	2008	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Adolescent caregivers (age 21 or less at time of enrollment with a child 18 months or younger) recruited from a single clinic from 2002-2005	102		NS difference in change in GWG by age	Yes			NS		10.1016/j.jpap.2007.08.006	
Jung, Y.M.	2017	Korea	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth to term infants and resided in a single city in South Korea	75		NS difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, or excessive) by mean maternal age; NS difference in total GWG by household income (<3,000,000 won vs ≥3,000,000 won)	No	NS		NS		10.7762/cnr.2017.6.1.27	
Kearney, M. H.	2004	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1985	Multi-site study with women in Massachusetts who were screened during pregnancy for intimate partner abuse (non-representative sample)	1 969	Abuse is a weak predictor of insufficient GWG (<15 lbs)	Abuse is also a weak predictor of smoking & substance use (alcohol, drugs)	No					S	Nursing Research 2004;53(1):36-45
Ketterlinus, R. D.	1990	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; National Center for Health Statistics 1980	Black or White, primiparous women enrolled in the National Longitudinal Survey of Work Experience of Youth; all women were between 13 and 30 years old	1 994	Significant difference in total GWG by age group (<15, 16-18, 19-21, 22+ yrs)		No				S	Journal of Adolescent Health Care 1990;11:423-31	
Khanolkar, A. R.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Medical record/birth certificate; IOM 2009	All women who gave birth in Washington State from 2006-08	181 948	Significant difference in adequacy of GWG according to education level (12th grade or less, high school graduate, some college, associates degree, bachelor's degree, postgraduate degree), age, ethnicity (White, Black, Native American, East Asian, Hispanic, South Asian, Hawaiian/Pacific Islander/other), marital status (married vs single/unknown), and parity (1, 2, 3 or more); total GWG also varied significantly between racial/ethnic groups	On average, Indigenous were the youngest, East Asian were the oldest	No	S	S	S	S*	S	10.1080/13557858.2017.1398312
Kieffer, E. C.	2001	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Black and Latina women in Detroit who received at least 4 prenatal care visits from January 1995 - December 1998	1 334	Higher odds of insufficient and lower odds of excessive GWG in Latina vs Black women; Black women had significantly higher GWG than Latina women		Yes				S	Journal of the American Medical Women's Association 2001;56(4):181-196	

Kinnunen, T. I.	2016	Norway	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women seeking prenatal care in Eastern Oslo from 2008-10	632	Eastern European had higher total GWG (as compared to Western European); negative relationship between GWG and education (<10 years vs university or college), and age (age range not identified, but population consisted primarily of adults)	NS difference in odds of excessive GWG between racial/ethnic groups; NS difference in GWG between Western European and South Asian, East Asian, Middle Eastern or African, and NS difference in total GWG between 10-12 yrs of education vs university/college education	No	S & NS				S*	S & NS	10.1007/s10995-016-1947-7	
Kirchengast, S.	2003	Austria	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Single-site study with primiparous women age 12-29 yrs who attended all prenatal check-ups and gave birth from 1985-1995 at a university clinic; adolescents age 12-16 had to have received psychosocial support	8 011		NS difference in total GWG between individuals <17 yrs, 17-19 yrs, or 20-29 yrs of age	No					NS		10.1002/ajhb.10139	
Koh, H.	2013	Singapore	Retrospective	Medical record; GWG guideline by Wong et al., 2000	All women who delivered at a specific hospital from Jan-Apr 2008 (approximately 30% of infants in Singapore are delivered at this hospital every year)	1 166	Higher odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate): age ≤ 19 years (as compared to 20-30 years), ethnicity (Malay vs Chinese), subsidized paying class for hospital (vs private paying class); higher odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate): ethnicity (Malay vs Chinese); lower odds of excessive GWG if older (31+ as compared to 20-30 years)	NS effect of parity on GWG adequacy (insufficient or excessive); NS effect of adolescent age (as compared to 20-30 years old) or paying class (subsidized vs private) on odds of excessive GWG; NS difference in GWG adequacy between Indian and Chinese ethnicities	No	S† & NS†		NS	S & NS	S & NS		10.1111/j.1447-0756.2012.02067.x	
Koleilat, M.	2013	USA	Retrospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Primarily Hispanic women, all with a low-income and enrolled in the Public Health Foundation Enterprises WIC Program in Southern California	23 840	Higher odds of excessive GWG if above federal poverty line (>100% vs <100% of federal poverty level); lower odds of excessive GWG if Spanish was preferred language (compared to English), higher age (no limit to population age) and if current health care coverage (as compared to no coverage)	NS effect on odds of excessive GWG if a woman has pending health care coverage vs no health care coverage	Yes	S				S*		10.1007/s10995-012-1140-6	
Kominiarek, M. A.	2018b	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Large multi-site study with random selection of women who gave birth at one of the sites from 2008-11	29 861	Significant differences in GWG adequacy (inadequate, adequate, excessive) according to age (mean age approx. 29 yrs), race/ethnicity (White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, Asian non-Hispanic, Hispanic, other), parity, and insurance type (private, government-assisted, uninsured)		No	S†		S	S*	S		10.1097/AOG.000000000002854	
Korencan, S.	2017	Slovenia	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	All primiparous Slovenian women aged up to 24 years who gave birth from 2008-12	13 663	Significant difference in GWG adequacy between adolescents and adults		No					S		10.1515/sjph-2017-0036	
Kowal, C.	2012	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 2010 (IOM 2009)	Respondents of the Canadian Maternity Experiences Survey of 2006, all of whom were ≥ 15 years old	6,233 (weighted to n=74,523)	Higher odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) if less than a high school education (compared to university graduate), being of lower-middle or middle income group (compared to upper-middle income group), not being married/not living with partner; higher odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate): immigrant, multiparous (2 or 3+ births vs 1); lower odds of insufficient GWG if lower-middle income (compared to upper-middle income), consumed alcohol during pregnancy; lower odds of excessive GWG if immigrant, from highest income group (vs upper-middle income), multiparous	NS difference in odds of GWG adequacy (insufficient or excessive vs adequate) according to ethnicity, age (<20, 30-39, 40+ yrs vs 20-29); NS difference in odds of excessive GWG if high school education or post secondary diploma (as compared to university graduate), being of lowest income group (as compared to upper-middle income), or consuming alcohol during pregnancy; NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG for lowest, middle and highest income groups (as compared to upper-middle income), for married vs unmarried women or according to education level	No	S & NS	S & NS	S & NS	S	NS	NS	S	10.1007/s10995-011-0771-3
Krukowski, R. A.	2013	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Black and White respondents of the Arkansas Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2004-08 who had adequate or excessive GWG	4 619	Lower odds of excessive GWG if Black (vs White), Hispanic (vs not), if on Medicaid at any point in pregnancy or multiparous (vs primiparous); higher odds of excessive GWG if married (vs not married)	NS difference in women with adequate vs excessive GWG according to age (age range not identified, but primarily adults [average age: 25.5 years]), initiation of prenatal care, number of prenatal care visits, adequacy of prenatal care utilization or level of education (high school degree or less)	No	NS	S	S	S	NS*	S	10.1089/jwh.2012.3998	
Kuo, C. P.	2010	Taiwan	Retrospective	Self-reported; Taiwan Bureau of Health Promotion	Adolescents (<20 years old) and adults (20-35 years old) included in Taiwan's Birth Registration Database of 2005	9 880	Significantly more common for adolescents to have insufficient GWG (<12 kg) as compared to adults		No					S		10.1111/j.1442-200X.2009.02979.x	
Kurzel, R. B.	1997	USA	Prospective	Method used for obtaining GWG unclear; no GWG guideline identified	Predominantly Hispanic, immigrant adolescents (age 13-19 years) and adults ≥ 20 years)	2 440	Higher total GWG in adolescent (vs adults 20+ yrs), and wider range of GWG		Yes					S		Annals New York Academy of Sciences 1997;365-7	

Laraia, B.	2013	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women aged ≥16 years participating in the multi-site Pregnancy, Infection, and Nutrition cohort in North Carolina from January 2001 - June 2005	1 041	Marginally food insecure combined with high dietary restraint have higher GWG (same effect when limited to low-income marginally food insecure); marginally food insecure combined with low dietary restraint have lower GWG (same effect when limited to low-income marginally food insecure)		Restraint evaluated by Revised Restraint Scale - proxy for an "unhealthy restraint"	No	St					10.1016/j.jada.2010.02.014
Larouche, M.	2010	Canada	Retrospective	Medical record; Health Canada 2010 (IOM 2009)	Women who delivered at a health centre in Montreal from January 1998 - December 2007	960	Latin American had significantly higher GWG than South Asian; non-immigrants had higher GWG than women who immigrated to Canada >10 years before pregnancy (if restricted to women without hypertension, NS difference in GWG)	NS difference in all GWG between all other racial/ethnic groups (Caucasian, Black, East Asian, West Asian/Arab); NS association between excessive GWG and recent immigration; NS difference in total GWG between non-immigrants and women who immigrated to Canada 10 years or less before pregnancy	960 pregnancies analyzed (represents 645 different women)	No		S & NS	S & NS			Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology 2010;32(9):829-36
Larranaga, I.	2013	Spain	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with pregnant women seeking prenatal care from 2004-08	2 607	Higher odds of GWG outside of recommendations (as compared to within recommendations) in lower occupational class (manual vs non manual)	NS difference between level of education (university vs primary or secondary education) and GWG outside of recommendations (compared adequate GWG to combined insufficient/excessive GWG)		No	NS					10.1007/s10995-012-1134-4
Leonard, S. A.	2017	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Women who were enrolled in the National Longitudinal Survey of Youth 1979 and gave birth from 1979-2012	7 539	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate or excessive) by race/ethnicity (White non-Hispanic/other, Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic)			No		S				10.1111/ijpo.12163
Lindberg, S.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women who delivered at UW Health from 2007-12	7 385	Factors increasing odds of excessive GWG: age 20-24, 25-29 (as compared to 30-34 years), neighborhood with low economic hardship (compared to moderate); decreased odds of excessive GWG: age 40+ (vs 30-34 yrs), Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic, or other non-Hispanic race/ethnicity (vs White non-Hispanic), having Medicaid (vs commercial insurance), living in a neighborhood with low economic hardship (vs moderate) factors increasing odds of insufficient GWG: age >40 (as compared to 30-34 years), Black non-Hispanic or other non-Hispanic race/ethnicity (as compared to White non-Hispanic), Medicaid (compared to commercial insurance), neighborhood with high economic hardship (compared to moderate)	NS effect of age 18-19, 20-24, 25-29, 35-39 yrs (vs 30-34 yrs), Hispanic ethnicity (vs White non-Hispanic), living in neighborhood with low economic hardship (vs moderate) on odds of insufficient GWG; NS effect of age 18-19 (vs 30-34 yrs) on odds of excessive GWG		No	St	S* & NS	S & NS		Obesity Causes and Consequences 2016;115(5):233-7	
Liu, J.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Black non-Hispanic, White non-Hispanic, or Hispanic women without prepregnancy hypertension who gave birth from 2004-06 in South Carolina	133 849	Higher odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) in Hispanic and Black non-Hispanic women (only in women who were underweight or had a normal BMI; Hispanic and Black non-Hispanic were compared to White non-Hispanic); lower odds of insufficient GWG in overweight Hispanic women; lower odds of excessive GWG in Black non-Hispanic (all BMI) and Hispanic (except underweight)	NS difference in odds of excessive vs adequate GWG in underweight Hispanic (as compared to underweight White non-Hispanic); NS difference in insufficient vs adequate GWG in overweight/obese Black non-Hispanic and obese Hispanic (as compared to White non-Hispanic)	Only 1 in 5 women gained within IOM guidelines	No		S & NS			10.1016/j.jannepidem.2014.02.009	
Longmore, D. K.	2018	Australia	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	White and Indigenous women; women with hyperglycemia were recruited through the NT Diabetes in Pregnancy Clinical Register, while a representative sample of women without hyperglycemia were recruited through antenatal clinics	877	Excessive GWG more prevalent in White, while insufficient GWG more prevalent in Indigenous (both outcomes only significant in women without hyperglycemia)	NS difference in GWG adequacy between Indigenous and White women who had maternal hyperglycemia		No		S & NS				10.1111/ijpo.12490
Loris, P.	1985	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; Morse et al. 1975 (standard GWG curve)	Adolescents age 13-19 years in the Sacramento area who attended adolescent-specific pregnancy clinics or programs from 1979-82	145	When father of baby reacted positively to pregnancy, GWG was significantly higher	NS difference in total GWG based on age (13-15, 16-17, 18-19 yrs), ethnic group (White, Hispanic, Black) or marital status (married vs not married)		Yes	NS	NS*	NS			Journal of the American Dietetic Association 1985;85(10):1296-1305
Lowell, H.	2010	Canada	Retrospective	Self-reported; Health Canada 1999 IOM 1990)	Respondents of the 2006 national Maternity Experiences Survey, all of whom were ≥15 years old	5 554	Significantly higher prevalence of excessive GWG with younger age (15-19, 20-24, and 25-29 years of age as compared to 35-39), primiparity, less than secondary education, Aboriginal and Canadian-born; higher prevalence of insufficient GWG in multiparous, low household income (as compared to high income) or foreign-born	NS difference in prevalence of insufficient GWG according to age (age range: 15-40+ years old), education (less than secondary, secondary, some postsecondary/diploma/certificate, university degree) or Aboriginal status; NS difference in prevalence of excessive GWG according to income		No	S & NS	S & NS	S	S & NS	S & NS	Statistics Canada Health Reports 2010;21(2)

Margerison-Zilko, C.	2014	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Participants of the 1979 National Longitudinal Survey of Youth, all of whom were 14-22 years of age in 1979	5 175	Effect of extreme unexpected economic contraction differed by race/ethnicity and education: increased risk of insufficient and excessive GWG if Black non-Hispanic or Hispanic (vs non-Black/non-Hispanic), and lower risk of excessive GWG if higher education (greater than high school as compared to high school)	NS effect of extreme unexpected economic contraction on risk of insufficient or excessive GWG throughout pregnancy when full sample analyzed together; when stratified: NS difference in risk of insufficient GWG by education and NS difference in risk of excessive GWG if lower education (less than high school vs high school)	No	S & NS	S	10.1016/j.annepidem.2014.02.014
Marsiglio, W.	1988	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; GWG ≤15lbs considered insufficient, ≥50lbs excessive	Women who participated in the National Longitudinal Survey of Labour Market Experience of Youth; sample weighted to be representative of a national cross-section of women age 19-27 years in 1984; women were primiparous at the time of their interview	6 015	Predictors of insufficient GWG: being Black (vs non Black), being ≤18 or 19-20 yrs old at time of birth (vs older); predictors of excessive GWG: low education in pregnant woman's mother (<12 years), age 19-20 at time of birth (vs ≥21 yrs)	NS effect of being Black, ≤18 years old on excessive GWG (vs ≥21 yrs); NS effect on insufficient GWG if pregnant woman's mother had <12 years of education; NS effect on insufficient or excessive GWG if Hispanic ethnicity, if White and economically disadvantaged (results not indicated for other racial groups), or if pregnant woman's mother had >12 years of education	No		S & NS S & NS	Journal of Marriage and the Family 1988;50(4):1023-36
McFarlane, J.	1996	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 1985	Primarily low-income women attending one of two public prenatal clinics in Texas and Maryland; ethnic composition: about 1/3 White, 1/3 Black, 1/3 Hispanic	1 058	Higher relative risk of insufficient GWG (<15lbs) if abused during pregnancy (vs not abused), or used alcohol/drugs	Abused women at higher risk of being <17 years old, unmarried, having infections, having less than 24 months between pregnancies, having anemia, smoking, using alcohol or drugs, late entry into prenatal care; White women experienced more frequent and severe abuse	Yes		S	Nursing Research 1996;45(1):37-42
Mehta, U.	2011	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Participants of the PIN study (Pregnancy, Infection and Nutrition study) who attended prenatal care at University of North Carolina hospitals from January 2001 - June 2005; all women were >16 years	1 192	Higher total GWG in White women (as compared to Black women) and higher mean adequacy of GWG in Black women (calculated as observed GWG/expected GWG); women less than 185% of poverty line had increased risk of insufficient GWG if they preferred a light body (vs average size); education: women with <16 years of education preferring a light body were at higher risk of excessive GWG (compared to those preferring an average size)	NS difference in risk of insufficient GWG if 185-<350% of poverty line or 350%+ of poverty line and have a light vs average body size preference; NS difference in risk of excessive GWG if high education (16+ years) and have a light vs average body size preference	No	S & NS	S	10.1007/s10995-010-0578-7
Mendez, D. D.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Black non-Hispanic Black and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in Allegheny County, Pennsylvania from 2003-10	55 608	High neighborhood socioeconomic disadvantage (NSED)(compared to low NSED) was associated with higher risk of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG); association between NSED and gestational weight loss: for White non-Hispanic, all levels of NSED compared to low NSED were associated with gestational weight loss (vs adequate GWG), while for Black non-Hispanic only high NSED compared to low NSED was associated with gestational weight loss	NSED not associated with excessive GWG; NS effect of mid-low or mid-high (vs low) NSED on insufficient GWG; NS association between mid-low or mid-high NSED (vs low) and gestational weight loss (vs adequate GWG) in Black non-Hispanic women	No		S & NS	10.1007/s10995-013-1339-1
Mendez, D. D.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Black non-Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in Allegheny County, Pennsylvania from 2003-10	73 061	White non-Hispanic women, but not Black non-Hispanic, had increased prevalence ratio for insufficient GWG if living in neighborhood with mid-high and high poverty (compared to low poverty); White non-Hispanic living in predominantly black or mixed neighborhoods were more likely to have insufficient GWG (vs White non-Hispanic women living in low % Black/predominantly White non-Hispanic neighborhoods)	NS relationship between neighborhood racial composition and GWG for Black women	No		S & NS	10.1016/j.ssmph.2016.09.008
Meng, Y.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Black women seeking prenatal care at one of two clinics from 2008-11, all of whom were ≥18 years of age and enrolled in Medicaid and/or the Special Supplemental Nutrition Program for Women, Infants, and Children	55	Higher GWG associated with lower parity, lower education (measured by grades of education)	NS association between GWG and age (age range: 18-36 years) or illegal drug use	Yes	S	S NS*	10.1177/1099800417743326
Meserole, L. P.	1984	USA	Prospective and retrospective	Medical record and measured; Committee on Maternal Nutrition weight gain curve	Primiparous adolescents (<19 years old) participating in one of two adolescent pregnancy programs in Washington state; a standard adult curve was used for comparison	80	Adolescents had significantly greater GWG than the adult standard curve; younger adolescents had lower GWG than older adolescents		No		S	Journal of Adolescent Health Care 1984;5(1):21-7

Messer, L. C.	2012	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	White non-Hispanic and Black non-Hispanic women who gave birth in one of four counties in North Carolina from 2001-05	23 533	Brief description of findings: higher odds of insufficient GWG; living in a neighborhood with higher physical incivilities, living in a neighborhood with more social space (only for White non-Hispanic); lower odds of insufficient GWG in neighborhood with higher walkability (only significant in one neighborhood-level for White non-Hispanic, but all levels for Black non-Hispanic)		Physical incivilities (ex: litter, graffiti, poor housing conditions) increase stress, fear of crime	No								S	Health and Place 2012;18(4):805-13		
Misra, V. K.	2010	USA	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Women who participated in the Behaviour in Pregnancy Study (BIPS) in Los Angeles; all were ≥18 years of age	435	Black women (as compared to non-Black women) had significantly higher rate of GWG in first half of pregnancy	NS difference in rate of GWG between Black and non-Black from 16-20 weeks pregnancy to 30-36 weeks of pregnancy	Significant difference in sample for certain characteristics: Black women were predominantly single, had lower education, used government assistance for medical payments and were multiparous; non-Black group composed of White non-Hispanic, Hispanic and Asian women	No								S & NS	10.3109/14767050903387037		
Morris, D. L.	1992	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate or medical record; Loris et al. 1985	White, Black, and Hispanic adolescents (≤17 years) who delivered at a University Hospital from January 1985 - December 1996	1 080	Significant difference in total GWG between White and Black women, with higher GWG in White	NS difference in total GWG for Hispanic vs Black or White	60% of Hispanics were married, whereas few White or Black women were married; older age in White women; lower education in Hispanic women	Yes								S & NS	Adolescent and Pediatric Gynecology 1992;5(1):32-38		
Most, J.	2018	USA	Prospective	Measured; no guideline identified	Women with obesity (BMI ≥30), between the ages of 18 and 40, who identified as Black non-Hispanic or White non-Hispanic	66		NS difference in rate of GWG in 2nd trimester (in g/week) between Black non-Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women		No								NS	10.1093/ajcn/nqy053		
Naiqiso, S. L. S.	2019	New Zealand	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Women enrolled in prenatal care with Counties Manukau Health from September 2004 - March 2016	604	Maori had higher odds of insufficient GWG; Pacific had higher odds of excessive GWG, while Indian had lower odds of excessive GWG (all racial/ethnic groups compared to European); multiparous (2 or 3+ births) had lower odds of excessive GWG (compared to nulliparous)	NS effect of parity on odds of insufficient GWG; NS effect of having had 1 previous birth vs no previous births on odds of excessive GWG; NS difference in odds of excessive or insufficient GWG between Asian and White women; NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG for Indian and Pacific women (vs European women); NS difference in odds of excessive GWG for Maori (vs European)		No								S & NS	New Zealand Medical Journal 2019;132(1497):37-45		
Nunnery, D.	2018	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Women attending a WIC clinic (for low-income women) in 2014 who were receiving WIC as a maternity client and were ≥18 years old	160	Predictors of excessive GWG (higher odds): being Black (compared to not Black)	In multivariate regression: NS association between monthly income (\$0-500, 501-1,000, 1,000+), employment status (working vs not working), education (high school or less vs more than high school), parity (primiparous vs multiparous), marital status (single/divorced/separated vs married/living together) and odds of excessive GWG		Yes	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS			S	10.1080/073993322017.1391263		
Ochsenbein-Kolble, N.	2007	Switzerland	Cross-sectional	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	White, Asian, and Black women at the Obstetric Outpatient Department at Zurich University Hospital from January 1996 - February 2000	4 034	Significantly lower GWG in Asian and Black (as compared to White); among White women: parity had a significant effect on GWG (effect on other race/ethnicities not noted)	NS effect of age on GWG in White women (effect on other race/ethnicities not noted)		No								S	NS*	S & NS	10.1016/j.ejogrb.2006.03.024
Park, J. H.	2011	Korea	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified (no official guidelines in Korea)	Single-site study of women who gave birth at a university hospital from 2005-07	2 311	Insufficient GWG (<10 kg) significantly more prevalent in multiparous women, women with lower education (12 yrs or less)	NS difference in adequacy of GWG according to age (age range not indicated, but mean age of 31.7), low economic status		No	S	NS						S	NS*	10.1111/j.1447-0756.2010.01332.x	
Pawlak, M.	2015	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in Colorado from 2007-10	230 698	Increased odds of insufficient GWG in Hispanic, Black, and other race/ethnicity (vs White non-Hispanic), parous women (1-2, or 3+ births vs 0), women living 0-9 years in USA (as compared to born in USA) and women with 0-7 or >12 prenatal care visits (as compared to 8-12); decreased odds of insufficient GWG if higher education (high school, some college, college or higher as compared to having some high school), older (25-34 vs 18-24 yrs), single/separated (vs married/living with partner); decreased odds of excessive GWG if Hispanic or other (compared to White non-Hispanic), older (25-34 or 35+ yrs vs 18-24 yrs), highest education (college or more vs some high school), single/separated (vs married/living with partner), parous (1-2 or 3+ births vs 0), low prenatal care (0-7 visits vs 8-12), foreign-born (as compared to USA-born); increased odds of excessive GWG if >12 prenatal care visits (vs 8-12 visits)	NS effect on odds of insufficient GWG if immigrated to USA 10+ years ago (as compared to USA-born) or age 35+ (vs 18-24 yrs); NS effect on excessive GWG if high school graduate or have some college (as compared to some high school), Black (vs White non-Hispanic); NS effect on insufficient or excessive GWG if adolescent (<18 years as compared to 18-24), consuming alcohol during pregnancy		No	S & NS		S	S	S*	S & NS	S & NS	S & NS		10.1007/s10903-013-9886-5	

Perry, R. L.	1996	USA	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescents (<16 years old), and adults (18-29 years old) who participated in the Camden Study	387	Significantly higher GWG in young adolescents (mean age: 14.7, SD 0.7 yrs); insufficient GWG significantly more common in adults/older adolescents (mean age: 19.8, SD 2.2 yrs) vs young adolescents		No								S	10.3109/1476705960 9018410
Platner, M. H.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Women who gave birth in New York City from 2008-2012	515 148	Significant differences in adequacy of GWG based on age (6 categories: <20, 20-29, 30-34, 35-39, 40-44, 45+), race/ethnicity (Black non-Hispanic, White non-Hispanic, Puerto Rican, other Hispanic, Asian/Pacific Islander, other, non-Hispanic with two or more races), education (<high school, high school, some college, college graduate or higher), parity (0 vs 1+), and insurance type (considered as a proxy for low-income; Medicaid, other, private, self-pay)		No	S	S†		S	S*	S			10.1097/AOG.000000 000003114
Power, M. L.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Multi-site study with primarily White non-Hispanic women in rural counties in Pennsylvania who gave birth from 2006-15	18 217	Total GWG decreased as parity increased	NS association between maternal age and total GWG (mean age: 26.9 yrs)	Yes				S	NS*				10.1089/jwh.2018.75 31
Provenzano, A. M.	2015	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 1990	Women who received prenatal care at a multispecialty group practice in Massachusetts (single-site)	2 128	Women who experienced material hardship in childhood: higher odds of having excessive GWG (than adequate) in unadjusted model - no longer significant once adjusted	NS association between adequacy of GWG and material hardship during pregnancy or from age 18 to pregnancy	No		NS†							10.1089/jwh.2014.50 16
Rambouskova, J.	2009	Czech Republic	Prospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Multi-site study involving women who gave birth from 2000-2002; study included Roma women (an ethnic minority in the Czech Republic) and non-Roma women	227		NS difference in total GWG by race/ethnicity (Roma vs non-Roma)	No					NS				10.1016/j.jneb.2008.0 4.360
Ranchod, Y. K.	2016	USA	Prospective	Self-reported; IOM 2009	White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, and Hispanic women who participated in the National Longitudinal Survey of Youth	6 199	Exposure to physical abuse and household alcohol abuse during childhood was associated with higher risk of excessive GWG		No								S	10.1016/j.jamepre.201 5.08.032
Ratan, B. M.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Low-income women with obesity who enrolled in prenatal care at a specific clinic in Houston, Texas from September 2013 August 2017; all women were receiving social assistance (CHIP Perinate or Medicaid)	772	Higher odds of excessive GWG if nulliparous (vs multiparous)	NS difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, excessive) according to race/ethnicity (Black, Hispanic, White, Asian) or age (age range: 15-35+; only exception: age 31-35 had higher odds of excessive GWG but became NS in multivariate analysis); NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG if nulliparous (as compared to multiparous); NS effect of relationship to father of infant on odds of excessive or insufficient GWG (married, partner, involved, not involved)	Yes			NS	S & NS	NS*	NS			10.1055/ s-0039-1678606
Reed, M. M.	2005	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1985	Undocumented immigrants (primarily Mexican) receiving Emergency Medicaid and women from the general population who gave birth in Colorado from 1998-99	118 904	Insufficient GWG (< 20 lbs) significantly more prevalent in undocumented immigrants (compared to other women)		No								S	10.1186/1471-2458-5 100
Restall, A.	2014	New Zealand, Australia, Ireland	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Multi-site cohort study with nulliparous women from 2004-11	1 950	Higher odds of excessive GWG if stopped smoking during pregnancy (as compared to non-smoker), if recent immigrant (within 5 years, as compared to not having immigrated within last 5 years) or if age 24 or less, 25-29, 30-34 years old (as compared to 35+)	NS difference in adequacy of GWG (not excessive vs excessive) according to ethnicity (White, Asian, Polynesian, Indian, other) or by socioeconomic index score (a New Zealand based index that includes income and education)	No					S*	NS	S		10.1155/2014/14839 1
Rosal, M. C.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Multi-site study involving White non-Latina and Latina women	571	Lower odds of excessive GWG in Latina (as compared to White non-Latina)	NS effect of age (15-19, 20-24, 30-34, and 35+ vs 25-29 yrs), parity (0 vs 1, 2, 3+ births), alcohol use, insurance (commercial/private vs public), employment at pregnancy onset (employed vs not employed) on odds of excessive or insufficient GWG; no association between marital status and general adequacy of GWG (looked at prevalence of 3 different GWG adequacy categories by whether women were divorced, married, or single); NS difference in odds of insufficient GWG between Latina and White non-Latina women	No		NS†	NS	NS	NS	S & NS			10.1155/2016/89849 28
Rosenberg, T. J.	2005	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Asian non-Hispanic, Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in New York City from 1999-2001	329 988	Significant differences in excessive GWG by race/ethnicity (compared prevalence of GWG <41 lbs vs 41+ lbs between Black non-Hispanic, White non-Hispanic, Asian non-Hispanic, and Hispanic)		No								S	10.2105/AJPH.2005.0 65680

Roville-Sausse, F.	2001	France	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Women who immigrated to France (from Turkey, Sub-Saharan Africa, North Africa, China, or Sri Lanka) and French nationals who attended prenatal care and gave birth at a specific hospital in Paris in 1997	559	When compared to non-immigrant French, all immigrant groups except Turkish experienced significantly lower GWG	NS difference in GWG between Turkish immigrants and non-immigrant French	No						S & NS	Revue d'Epidemiologie et de Sante Publique 2001;49(5):439-447
Sackoff, J. E.	2015	USA	Cross-sectional	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Nulliparous women who gave birth in New York City from 1994-2004 and had a second pregnancy during that period; all women were either Black non-Hispanic, White non-Hispanic, Hispanic, or Asian/Pacific Islander	115 651	Significantly lower GWG in Asian/Pacific Islanders (as compared to White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic) and lower proportion of Asian/Pacific Islander women with GWG ≥40 lbs and ≥50 lbs (As compared to other 3 groups)	Similar total GWG for White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, and Hispanic, and similar proportions of women gaining ≥40 lbs and ≥50 lbs	No						S & NS	10.1007/s10995-014-1639-0
Sangi-Haghpeykar, H.	2014	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Hispanic women who delivered at a specific hospital in Texas	282	Higher odds of excessive GWG if USA born (vs non-US born), unmarried (vs married); lower odds of insufficient GWG if lower social support	NS difference in adequacy of GWG according to mean age (age range not indicated, but mean age of 28.4 years), education (in years), number of previous pregnancies, number of living children, or alcohol use during pregnancy; level of social support did not affect prevalence of excessive vs adequate GWG; prevalence of insufficient vs adequate GWG not affected by being born in US vs elsewhere	Yes	NS	S	NS	NS*		S & NS	10.1007/s10995-013-1248-3
Savitz, D. A.	1990	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; no GWG guideline identified	Women who gave birth in 1980 in the US, were married, and were recorded in the National Natality Survey	5 927	Working women (as compared to non-working women) were less likely to have very low GWG (<11 lbs); women in managerial, professional and technical occupations (as compared to sales and clerical workers) were less likely to have very low GWG (<11 lbs vs 21-40 lbs); operatives were more likely to have low GWG (11-20 lbs vs 21-40 lbs) (as compared to sales and clerical workers)	Unemployed women had lowest education, income and started prenatal care later	No							American Journal of Epidemiology 1990;132(5):933-945
Scholl, T. O.	1995	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Women age 12-29 with a low-income and a normal BMI; most women were Puerto Rican Hispanic or Black (data from Camden Study)	274	Excessive rate of GWG (as compared to low or moderate rate of GWG) significantly more prevalent in primiparous and age 15 or less (other age groups: 16-18, 19-29)	NS association between adequacy of GWG rate and race/ethnicity (Puerto-Rican, Black, White) and Medicaid use	Yes		NS†	S	S	NS		Obstetrics & Gynecology 1995;86(3):423-7
Scholl, T. O.	1984	USA	Retrospective	Medical record; no GWG guideline identified	Low-income, Black and Hispanic women who attended a specific prenatal center in Camden and gave birth in 1980; most participants were receiving welfare and were enrolled in the Supplemental Food Program for Women, Infants, and Children; half the participants were ≤15 years old, and the other half was ≥20 years old	64	Higher prevalence of insufficient GWG in adolescents		Yes				S			Journal of Adolescent Health Care 1984;5(3):167-71
Schumacher, T. L.	2018	Australia	Prospective	Measured; IOM 2009	Indigenous women, or women carrying an Indigenous child, who sought prenatal care at one of three sites in New South Wales	110	Multiparity associated with higher GWG	NS relationship between GWG adequacy and age (no age range identified; mean age 25.1 years)	Yes			S	NS*			10.1016/j.midw.2018.01.017
Shieh, C.	2014	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; trimester-specific GWG guideline from Fontaine et al. 2012	Black and Hispanic women ≥18 years of age enrolled in prenatal care at one of two health centers in a large Midwest city from August 2012 - January 2013	56	Excessive GWG more likely in Black (vs Hispanic)	NS difference in total GWG between Black and Hispanic	Yes						S & NS	10.1080/07370016.2014.868730
Shrestha, D.	2019	USA	Prospective	Measured and medical records; IOM 2009	Women enrolled in the National Institute of Child Health and Human Development Fetal Growth Study from July 2009 - January 2013; women were either White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic, or Asian/Pacific Islander	1 945	GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, excessive) varied by race/ethnicity (White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic, Hispanic, Asian)		No					S		10.1002/oby.22499

Siega-Riz, A. M.	1997	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Hispanic, primarily low-income women attending public prenatal clinics and who participated in a prematurity prevention project	6 114	Multivariate linear regression model for total GWG: positive association with primiparous (at any age vs multiparous at 20-29 yrs), education, being divorced (vs married), and being a US-born Hispanic; negative association with being multiparous (only when younger than 20 or older than 29 yrs vs multiparous at 20-29 yrs), being single (vs married), and physical abuse by baby's father Multivariate logistic regression for insufficient GWG (<21 lbs for underweight/normal weight women, <10 lbs for overweight/obese women): For overweight/obese women: increased risk of insufficient GWG if physical abuse by baby's father; for normal/underweight, decreased odds of insufficient GWG if primiparous (only if <20 or 20-29 yrs)	NS association between total GWG (for all women) and being single (vs married), multiparous at <20 yrs old or >29.1 yrs old, or of Mexican descent NS effect on odds of insufficient GWG (for all women): multiparity at any age, education (<8 yrs or >12 yrs), marital status, being of Mexican descent, being a US-born Hispanic; specific to overweight/obese women: NS effect of being primiparous (any age); in underweight/normal weight women: NS effect of abuse by baby's father, being primiparous (if >29 years old)	Yes	S & NS	Journal of the American Dietetic Association 1997;97(11):1264-8									
Singh, G. K.	2018	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; no GWG guideline identified	Women who gave birth in the USA in 2014-15 and were included in the national nativity files	7 966 573	Excessive GWG (>40lbs) significantly more prevalent in Samoan, Hawaiian, Cuban, Puerto Rican, White non-Hispanic, Black non-Hispanic and American Indian/American Native compared to all Asian subgroups (Chinese, Japanese, Filipino, Asian Indian, Korean, Vietnamese)		No								S	10.1155/2018/7897189		
Sowers, M. F.	2000	USA	Prospective	Measured; IOM 1990	Adolescents and adults participating in a study of pregnancy and lactation in Camden, New Jersey	252		NS difference in total GWG by race/ethnicity (White, Black, Hispanic)	No									NS	Obstetrics & Gynecology 2000;96(2):189-93	
Stevens-Simon, C.	1997	USA	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Black adolescents age 13-17 years at conception	108		NS difference in rate of GWG (in kg/week) between younger and older adolescents (<16 yrs old vs 16-18 yrs old)	Yes									NS	10.3109/14767059709161959	
Stevens-Simon, C.	1993a	USA	Prospective	Measured; no GWG guideline identified	Black adolescents (<20 yrs old at conception) with a low-income who gave give from 1986-1989	141		NS difference in total GWG (adjusted to represent a 40-week gestational period) between younger and older adolescents (<16 yrs old vs 16-19 yrs old)	Yes									NS	Pediatrics 1993;92(6):805-9	
Stogianni, A.	2019	Sweden	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Women with and without diabetes who were admitted to a specific hospital in Kronoberg from January 2009 - December 2012	280	Multiparity reduced odds of high GWG (categorized as GWG ≥8 kg) in women without diabetes	Among women with diabetes or without diabetes, maternal age >30 yrs, marital status (living alone vs not), and ethnicity (Asian or Black vs White) were not significantly associated with high GWG (GWG ≥8 kg); in women with diabetes: parity not associated with high GWG	No			NS	S & NS	NS*				NS	10.1186/s12884-019-2269-8	
Stotland, N. E.	2006	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; IOM 1990	Women with a normal or low pre-pregnancy BMI who gave birth at the University of California, San Francisco Medical Center from 1976 to 2001	15 101	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (insufficient, adequate, excessive) between racial/ethnic groups (White, Black, Latina, Asian) based on kg gained per week; no post-hoc analysis conducted		No										S	Obstetrics & Gynecology 2006;108:1448-55
Sukanich, A. C.	1986	USA	Retrospective	Medical records; no GWG guideline identified	Women who delivered at a single hospital in Pittsburgh from 1970-1977 without medical problems prior to pregnancy	694		NS difference in total GWG by age (<16 vs 20-24 yrs old)	No										NS	Pediatrics 1986;78(1):31-6
Tabet, M.	2017	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Adolescents (<20 years old) who gave birth in the USA in 2012	171 573	Significant differences in adequacy of GWG (insufficient, adequate, excessive) between women of different racial/ethnic groups (White, Black, Indigenous, Asian, Hispanic)	The majority of women in every racial/ethnic group has excessive GWG	Yes										S	10.1016/j.jpap.2016.08.004
Tovar, A.	2012	USA	Prospective	Medical record; IOM 2009	Hispanic (Puerto Rican or Dominican Republic heritage) women who were either born in the Caribbean Island, had a parent born in the Caribbean Islands, or at least 2 grandparents born in the Caribbean Islands; all women gave birth at Baystate Medical Center from 2006-11	952	Higher odds of excessive GWG if US born (compared to Puerto Rico/Dominican Republic born), and higher total GWG if US born	NS effect of acculturation (measured using the Psychological Acculturation Scale) on total GWG or GWG adequacy; NS effect of being born in US vs Puerto Rico/Dominican Republic on odds of insufficient GWG	Yes										S & NS	10.1186/1471-2393-12-133
Vinkoor-Imler, L. C.	2011	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Black non-Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth from 2001-05 in one of four counties North Carolina and were enrolled in the third Pregnancy, Infection, and Nutrition Study (PIN3)	23 304	Insufficient GWG (<15 lbs) more likely if higher quartiles of social space [only in White non-Hispanic]; lower odds of inappropriate GWG if neighborhoods have high walkability; excessive or insufficient (for Black non-Hispanic: only insufficient) GWG associated with neighborhoods having high amounts of physical incivility	Physical incivility: litter, graffiti, poor housing conditions; social spaces: public spaces for socializing	No										S	10.1016/j.socscimed.2011.08.012

Virji, S. K.	1991	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; no GWG guideline identified	A portion of women who had a live birth in 1980 in the US and were recorded in the National Natality Survey; births that resulted in adoption and births of non-US residents were excluded; women with low birthweight infants were intentionally oversampled	5 823	Significant differences in GWG (<20 lb vs >20 lb) between White and Black women, with lower GWG (<20 lbs) more common in Black	No											American Journal of Perinatology 1991;8(5):347-53
Walker, L. O.	2014	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Hispanic and White non-Hispanic women who gave birth in 2009 in Texas and were ≥18 years old	250 857	Increased odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) if younger (18-24 yrs vs 25+ yrs), unmarried (vs married), less than high school education (vs high school or more), Hispanic (vs White non-Hispanic); decreased odds of insufficient GWG if primiparous (vs multiparous); increased odds of excessive GWG if younger (18-24 yrs vs 25+ yrs), married, lower education (less than high school vs high school or more), primiparous; decreased odds of excessive GWG if on Medicaid, not born in USA, Hispanic (vs White non-Hispanic)	No	S	S† & NS†	S	S	S*	S	S & NS				10.1111/1552-6909.12467
Walker, L. O.	2009	USA	Retrospective	Self-reported; IOM 1990	Hispanic women who responded to the New Mexico Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System from 2000-03, all of whom were ≥18 years old	1 988	Higher odds of excessive GWG (vs adequate GWG) if primiparous (no previous live birth vs previous live birth); lower odds of insufficient GWG (vs adequate GWG) if primiparous or enrolled in WIC services; significant differences in general GWG adequacy according to income (divided into quartiles of annual family income: \$0-10,400, 10,400-17,186, 17,186-30,000, >30,000), education (0-8 yrs, 9-11, 12, 13-15, ≥16 yrs), immigration status (US born vs not)	Yes	S & NS	S & NS	NS	S	NS*		S & NS	NS			10.1111/j.1552-6909.2009.01036.x
Walker, L. O.	2002	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Women who delivered at a single hospital with a parity of 3 or less and who had Medicaid coverage for prenatal care	305	NS difference in total GWG by race/ethnicity (White, Black, Hispanic)	Yes							NS				JOGNN 2002;31:263-274
Wang, C. S.	1999	Taiwan	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; no GWG guideline identified	Adolescent (<20 years old) and adult primigravidas who gave birth from June 1994 - May 1995 in Kaohsiung County	1 146	Significant difference in GWG (<12 kg vs 12+ kg) by maternal age (<18 yrs, 18-19, 20-24, 25+ yrs)	No						S*					Journal of the Formosan Medical Association 1999;98:415-21
Wang, S. C.	2012	Taiwan	Retrospective	Self-reported; Taiwan Bureau of Health Promotion	Primiparous adolescents (<20 years old) and adults (35-49 years old) who gave birth in Taiwan in 2005	1 236	Odds of insufficient GWG (12 kg or less) significantly higher in adolescents (<20 years) as compared to adults (>35 years)	No						S					10.1016/j.jpuhe.2012.08.014
Wells, C. S.	2006	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 1990	Respondents of the 2000-02 Colorado Pregnancy Risk Assessment Monitoring System	4 528	Higher odds of insufficient GWG if <12 years or 12 yrs of education (as compared to >12 years), parous (any previous live birth vs no previous live birth); lower odds of insufficient GWG if consumed alcohol during pregnancy; higher odds of excessive GWG if completed 12 years of education (vs >12 yrs); lower odds of excessive GWG if parous	No	S & NS	NS†		S	NS	NS					10.1007/s10995-005-0034-2
Woolfolk, C. L.	2016	USA	Retrospective	Birth certificate; IOM 2009	Population-based cohort of adolescents who gave birth in the USA in 2012	211 403	Significant difference in GWG adequacy (prevalence of insufficient, adequate, excessive) according to race/ethnicity (White, Black, Hispanic, other), age (≤ 15 vs 15-19 yrs), and WIC status (yes/no)	Yes		S†				S	S				10.1038/jp.2016.149
Wright, C.	2013	USA	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; IOM 2009	Low-income urban women enrolled in a community-based participatory research study; all women attended a social service and advocacy agency for low-income women	101	Lower GWG associated with positive response to locus of control on GWG, self-efficacy for eating healthy; Hispanic women were significantly more likely to have adequate GWG than excessive GWG	Yes			NS			NS*	S & NS				10.1353/hpu.2013.0004
Yang, M. S.	2006	Taiwan	Cross-sectional	Self-reported; no GWG guideline identified	Indigenous women in Southern and Eastern Taiwan who gave birth from January-December 2003 at one of 10 hospitals	1 143	Lower GWG in women with physical abuse by intimate partner during pregnancy (as compared to no physical abuse)	Yes								S			10.1016/j.jpuhe.2006.01.006
Zheng, Z.	2019	USA	Retrospective	Medical records or self-reported; IOM 2009	Women from the Boston Birth Cohort	5 568	Black non-Hispanic had lowest total GWG (as compared to White non-Hispanic, after controlling for confounders)	No							S				10.1089/jwh.2017.6574

† Study used a proxy measure for income (e.g., use of social assistance program)

* Study did not specifically indicate differences in GWG between adolescents and adults